

FronTowns: Think big on small frontier towns: Alto Alentejo and Alta Extremadura leonesa (13th - 16th centuries)

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Authors: Yulia Karimova, Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo Silva, Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán Costa

Affiliation: INESC TEC, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Universidade Aberta

ORCID iD:

Yulia Karimova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1015-6709>,
Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo Silva <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4880-094X>
Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán Costa
<http://orcid.org/0000-0001-9335-9386>

Project abstract: This project has been drawn up in 2 confluent approaches. The 1st aims to identify the role played by small towns in the establishment of borders between Portugal and Castile, as well as in relationships with more distant areas. This assessment will be conducted through an exploration of all the links and flows established, made possible or obstructed by the geographical conditions between these towns, whether material, political or mental. Although the geographic and chronological frameworks are not, a priori, very strict in nature, the 1st focuses on Portugal's Alto Alentejo and León's Alta Extremadura, and the second extends from the 13th to the 16th centuries. The 2nd perspective analysis focuses on 2 of these towns, Castelo de Vide and Cáceres, which are located on each side of the border. This 2nd stage was carried out through a study and reconstruction of the way in which the urban space of these two towns has developed. The 2 scales of observation - macro and micro – require a multidisciplinary Iberian team to be established, composed of historians, archaeologists, art historians, urbanism historians and computer science specialists. We intend to test some explanatory hypotheses, applying variables used to adapt Jean-Luc Fray's method (see Lit. Review). As a means of enabling us to view and enhance the results of this methodology, an existing georeferenced database (Mercator-e) has been used, and new layers incorporated according to the connectivity variables explored. The 2nd part of the approach - micro - has been carried out using 3D modeling and animation, to observe how links and flows are reflected in these two towns' urban areas. Market and exchange areas, as well as those used for socializing and hosting, were all reconstructed, in addition to roads and meeting places/yards and their relationship with the residential fabric. In using this 2nd route of analysis, the challenge faced is to produce outputs that successfully impact the scientific community, decision-makers and society. The results will be published on a portal connected to Casa de Velázquez that will also promote joint advanced training and cement the international network of researchers.

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1. Output summary (Data collection)

This project is divided into **2 parts** with different types of data, collecting methods and management rules. This project is financed by FCT - Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology with grant number - PTDC/HAR-HIS/3024/2020, and responds to all existing requirements related to open access, Research Data Management and Protection of Personal Data.

All members of the project follow the established, updated and monitored Data Management Plan during the development of the work and after its finalization.

Collected data during this project is important in different dimensions: scientific, economic, education and cultural; and for many scientific domains: history, archaeology, art history, history of urbanism, and computer science.

This research project and data can help to identify the role played by small Portuguese and Castilian border towns (see Figure 1), by studying their urban space and the links and flows between these towns. The information gathered will also allow us to do 3D reconstitutions and animations of Castelo de Vide and Cáceres. There are similar studies, but not for the towns under studies, so it raises the value of the data that we will collect. The importance of these projects and data also is increasing due to the “openness” perspective, according to open science policy. Moreover, according to FAIR principles, we will make our data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable by other researchers and students.

Figure 1. Map of the borders' towns under study

This **1st part** of the project will include: **RAW data** and **processed data**.

The RAW data will include: documentation related to the towns under study. It

includes information about their urban space, primary and secondary roads, means of communication and transportation, circulation of peoples and commodities, and communication and political networks, among other themes. The sources will be collected from different Portuguese and Spanish archives. The information gathered and studies done will not include any sensitive data. They will be focused only on the analysis of the urban space and the links and flows between the Alto Alentejo and Alta Extremadura's frontier towns.

The processed data will include: all RAW data indicated above after their processing (e.g. through the use of a database and programs like ArcGis and Inkscape).

The **2nd part** of the project will include: **RAW data** and **processed data**.

The RAW data in this project will include: processed data from 1st part of the project, 3D models, 3D reconstructions of Castelo de Vide and Caceres, associated publications, GIS shapefiles, 3D images, database, and videos, among others. The cartographic translation of the various links and flows established between the small towns will be carried out using ArcGIS {<https://www.arcgis.com/index.html>} and InksCape {<https://inkscape.org/pt/>}.

The processed data will include: all RAW data indicated above after their processing.

Other additional documents - Project Proposal, different types of agreements, emails exchanged (will be stored on projects email: frontowns@fcs.unl.pt), requested reports for the funder, copies of the Postdoc contract process, hiring of the team process, relevant emails exchange with FCT, internal documents for project management (e.g. applications for MA and PhD scholarships within the project, MA and PhD scholarship contracts, etc.). Some of them will be stored on the external disk, others on the research unit archive (Institute for Medieval Studies). More detailed information about these documents and their management will be added on the following versions of the DMP.

RAW data and processed data will be accessible to all project members and will be available to other researchers after the 4-year period, after the finalizing PhD and Master's theses related to this data.

Processed data will be made available to anyone until the end of the funding period.

Responsibilities

Supervisors of the project: Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán da Costa (PI) ; Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo da Silva (CO-PI)

Research team: (Grant 1; Grant 2; Grant 3) will be indicated on the following DMP; Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán da Costa; Ana Cristina Encarnação Santos Leitão; Ana Filipa Firmino Sequeira Pinto Roldão; António Fernando Vasconcelos Cunha Castro Coelho; Daniel Ribeiro Alves; Elena de Ortueta Hilberath; Florencio-Javier García Mogollón; Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo da Silva; Inês Sofia Lourenço Olaia; José Fabián Cuesta Gómez; Julian Clemente Ramos; Leonel Caseiro Morgado; Luis Vicente Clemente-Quijada; Maria Luísa Pires do Rio Carmo Trindade; Pau de Soto; Pedro Jorge Couto Cardoso; Pedro Miguel Araújo Correia Pinto.

Responsible entity:

- NOVA University Lisbon, School of Social Sciences and Humanities
- Institute for Medieval Studies, NOVA University Lisbon
- CHAM. Center for Humanities, NOVA University Lisbon
- Digital Humanities Lab, NOVA University Lisbon
- The Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science
- Center for History of the University of Lisbon
- University of Extremadura
- School of Higns Hispanic and Iberian Studies / Casa de Velázquez

Responsible for the collection:

for processing data: MA grant (1); MA grant (2); PhD Grant (1); Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán da Costa; Ana Cristina Encarnação Santos Leitão; Ana Filipa Firmino Sequeira Pinto Roldão; Elena de Ortueta Hilberath; Florencio-Javier García Mogollón; Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo da Silva; Inês Sofia Lourenço Olaia; Julian Clemente Ramos; Luis Vicente Clemente-Quijada; Pedro Miguel Araújo Correia Pinto.

for preservation data: Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán da Costa (PI) ; Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo da Silva (CO-PI)

Responsible for publishing and sharing data: Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán da Costa (PI) ; Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo da Silva (CO-PI)

Responsible for DMP creation, update and monitoring: Yulia Karimova (ylaleo@gmail.com); Gonçalo Miguel Correia Melo Silva (gmsilva@fcsb.unl.pt), Adelaide Maria Pacheco Lopes Pereira Millán Costa (Adelaide.Costa@uab.pt).

All partners and members of the project need to agree with the created DMP and the rules defined therein. The DMP will be created according to the recommendations of the “FCT”, which in turn, follows RDM and GDPR requirements, such as open-science and FAIR principles.

FAIR data

1. Findability

To ensure that the data is findable it will be described according to the Dublin Core standard is a metadata standard aimed at describing digital objects (<http://dublincore.org/>) and the OAI-PMH - Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (<https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>).

All processed data of 2 parts will be deposited on the project website (that is under development) and the universities repositories: the Nova University Lisbon, University of Coimbra and the INESC TEC that allow the DOI and/or Handle assignment. Each published dataset of the project will have Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) assigned by the chosen research data repository to make datasets more findable, accessible and reusable by others.

Information related to version control will also be added later on the next version of the DMP.

2. Accessibility

The RAW data will only be accessible to team members and will be stored on the project website, database, external disk and the repository of the Nova University Lisbon (Repositórios da Universidade Nova de Lisboa for the necessary period to fulfil the purposes for which they were collected and processed, namely scientific research and publishing.

The RAW data will not be published and will be destroyed after 5 years.

The processed data of all parts of the project will be open without any restrictions on the project website (which is under development), the portal of the Casa de Velázquez, and the data repository (that will be defined later) with DOI assignment, but only after publishing the respective papers. In other words, there will be an embargo period. Moreover, the processed data also will be stored on an external disk for 5 years after the conclusion of the project. This external disk will be preserved at the Institute for Medieval Studies.

3. Interoperability

To ensure the interoperability of the metadata, we will use the DCMI schema (<https://www.dublincore.org/schemas/>), Data Cite (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) and OAI-PMH (<https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>).

To ensure the interoperability of the data the preferred file formats for sharing will be *.xls/.xlsx, *.doc/.docx and Geographic Information System (GIS) acceptable formats.

4. Reusability

The processed shared data can be reusable without any restrictions (but only after the publishing of the papers related to the data) and any limit of time. They will be publicly available at the data repository (to be defined later) with license Share-Alike, which allows to (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>):

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format;

Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

Under the following terms:

Attribution — You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

ShareAlike — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the same license as the original.

No additional restrictions — You may not apply legal terms or technological measures that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Data security

1. Data recovery processing, secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The RAW and processed data will be stored on the project website, database and external disk. The backups will be done by the university's IT teams. Since the data do not contain any sensitive, personal or private information can be preserved in the long term.

2. Coverage of the ethics review procedure context

Because the data do not contain any sensitive, personal and private information, no Ethics Committee authorization or Data Protection Officer approval is required.

Other matters

The DMP will be monitored at least every 6 months. Monitorization will focus on registering the needed changes in all aspects related to the research data management issues. Moreover, it can also clarify the aspects related to the publication of the datasets on which data repository and their detailed description.

The project website (<https://frontowns.fcsh.unl.pt/>) will be one of the tools to disseminate and communicate the results of the project. More information will be added later.

This DMP will be published on Zenodo with DOI assignment and will be citable.

IPR ownership of data produced during the project is from the project team, however, all communications that refer to project results should mention the collaboration between the team of Portugal and Spain, and "FCT". All team members have the right to publish and disseminate the results generated under the Project with the authors' acknowledgement.

Complementary information

The expected data size for preservation will be defined later.

All communication in the project is carried out through the Moodle platform (<https://elearning.fcsh.unl.pt/flv/course/view.php?id=308>).